

Influence of inert gas on isoconversion curves and equilibrium conversion

Valeriu Voiculescu, Monica Mateescu, Serban Blejoiu and Petre Rotaru*

University of Craiova, A. I. Cuza 13, 1100 Craiova, Romania

E-mail : protaru@central.ucv.ro Fax : 40-251-415077

Manuscript received 21 January 2002, revised 14 November 2002, accepted 20 November 2002

Presence of inert gas has no influence on equation that one uses to calculate the isoconversion curves with $K_x = \text{constant}$. The curve with $K_x = 1$ (or $\Delta G_T^P = 0$) is called 'curve of normal null affinity'. In case of reactions with volume change, that take place in isothermal-isobaric conditions, the influence of inert gas on conversion ξ is maximum, if the reactions take place in conditions of temperature and pressure situated nearly the curve of normal null affinity. For mentioned reactions, the change of conversion $\Delta\xi$ increases with the relative change of volume $\Delta n/n_g$.

Many equilibrium reactions in gaseous phase of practical importance take place in presence of inert gas. This is the case of the ammonia synthesis :

where 'In' represents the inert gas (which is argon).

In oxidation reactions with air, nitrogen is also inert gas,

The inert gas is present in the reaction system and, as a particular feature, it does not react with any of the substances participating in the reaction.

In this paper, we have analyzed the influence of inert gas on isoconversion curves with $K_x = \text{constant}$ and equilibrium conversion ξ , considering that gaseous phase has an ideal behavior.

In case of equilibrium reaction that take place in gaseous phase or in solid-gas phases, which develop with change of volume, the isoconversion curves with $K_x = \text{constant}$ in variable pressure p (atm) and temperature T , can be calculated by applying the relation¹,

$$\ln p = - \frac{\ln K_x}{\Delta n} - \frac{\Delta G_T^0}{\Delta n RT} \quad (1)$$

where K_x represents the equilibrium constant in terms of mole fractions, Δn is the change of the amount of gas that accompanies the relation, R the general constant of gases and ΔG_T^0 the Gibbs free energy of reaction, at temperature T and pressure $p = 1$ atm. The quantity ΔG_T^0 is calculated with the relation,

$$\Delta G_T^0 = \Delta H_{298}^0 + \Delta \bar{C}_p^0 (T - 298) - T \Delta S_{298}^0 - T \Delta \bar{C}_p^0 \ln \quad (2)$$

where ΔH_{298}^0 and ΔS_{298}^0 are standard enthalpy of reaction and standard reaction entropy, respectively, and \bar{C}_p^0 is the average molar heat capacity at $p = 1$ atm, for the interval of temperature (298– T).

In eqn. (2), the terms containing $\Delta \bar{C}_p^0$ are always of opposite sign and satisfactorily compensate for most chemical reactions; that is why, in case that molar heats $\bar{C}_p^0(T)$ are not known, we can apply the approximate relation,

$$\Delta G_T^0 = \Delta H_{298}^0 - T \Delta S_{298}^0 \quad (3)$$

The free enthalpy of reaction ΔG_T^P , at temperature T and pressure p , is linked to the equilibrium constant K_x by the relation,

$$\ln K_x = -\Delta G_T^P / RT \quad (4)$$

For $K_x = 1$ (or $\Delta G_T^P = 0$) in eqn. (1), we obtain the equation of normal null affinity curve as it follows :

$$\ln p = - \frac{\Delta G_T^0}{\Delta n RT} \quad (5)$$

This curve presents theoretical importance. By representing the curve with $K_x = 1$ in the $\ln p$ - T plane, we can see two areas. On one side of the curve, $\Delta G_T^P < 0$ and $K_x > 1$, signifying that equilibria are displaced towards products or complete reactions; on the other side, $\Delta G_T^P > 0$, $0 < K_x < 1$, which means that the reactions take place with lower conversions or they are impossible thermodynamically.

By differentiating eqn. (5) with respect to temperature, we obtain the slope of the normal null affinity curve,

$$\left(\frac{d \ln p}{dT} \right)_{K_x} = \frac{\dot{\Delta H}_T^0}{\Delta n RT^2} \quad (6)$$

where ΔH_T^0 represents the enthalpy of reaction at tempera-

ture T and pressure $p = 1$ atm. Relation (6) can also be obtained by differentiating eqn. (1) with respect to temperature, with the imposed condition that $K_x = \text{constant}$. Thus, at the same temperature, all curves of isoconversion $K_x = \text{constant}$ have the same slope, which is identical to the slope of the normal null affinity curve, and the curves $K_x = \text{constant}$ have the same shape as the curve of normal affinity $K_x = 1$ (Figs. 1–3).

Other particularities of curves $K_x = \text{constant}$ have been discussed².

Results and discussion

Eqns. (1)–(6) are correct when the reaction takes place in presence of inert gas – paying attention to the fact that, in this case, total pressure p also includes the partial pressure

Fig. 1. Isoconversion curves $K_x = \text{constant}$ for the ammonia synthesis reaction : $\text{N}_2 + 3\text{H}_2 \leftrightarrow 2\text{NH}_3$.

Fig. 2. Family of curves $K_x = \text{constant}$ in case of reaction : $\text{MgCO}_3(\text{s}) \leftrightarrow \text{MgO}(\text{s}) + \text{CO}_2$.

Fig. 3. Curves of isoconversion $K_x = \text{constant}$ for reaction : $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}(\text{s}) \leftrightarrow \text{NH}_3 + \text{HCl}$.

of the inert gas. That is why the isoconversion curves $K_x = \text{constant}$ are the same, independently of the fact that the reaction takes place in presence or absence of inert gas. This phenomenon can be explained by taking into account the fact that the value of the equilibrium constant K_x depends only on temperature T and pressure p , corresponding to the reaction. If the presence of inert gas does not modify these parameters (as it happens in case of reactions taking place in isothermal-isobaric conditions), then any of the isoconversion curves with $K_x = \text{constant}$, is defined by the same eqn. (1).

Fig. 1 presents the isoconversion curves $K_x = \text{constant}$ for the ammonia synthesis reaction, with the variance $l = 3$. The points of the curves were calculated by using eqns. (1) and (2), with the necessary reported data³.

The equilibrium conversion ξ corresponds to the stoichiometric mixture of reactants, in absence of inert gas and were calculated by using the relation,

$$\xi = x_{\text{NH}_3} / (x_{\text{NH}_3} + 2 x_{\text{N}_2})$$

where x_i represents the mole fraction. The domain of inside border corresponds to Haber-Bosch synthesis.

The chemical equilibrium can be attained for any values of temperature T and pressure p and therefore there are infinity of curves with $K_x = \text{constant}$. Such is the case of other chemical reactions with variance $l \geq 2$, as the independent parameters are T and p (plus the composition parameters).

The disposition of the curves $K_x = \text{constant}$ in the $\ln p$ - T plane corresponds to the eqns.,

$$\left(\frac{\partial \ln K_x}{\partial T} \right)_p = \frac{\Delta H_T^0}{RT^2} \quad (7)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \ln K_x}{\partial P}\right)_T = -\frac{\Delta V}{RT} = -\frac{\Delta n}{p} \quad (8)$$

where ΔV represents the change of volume that accompanies the reaction. For example, in case of the ammonia synthesis reaction, which is exothermic with volume decrease, the equilibrium constants (K_x) have increasing values, as pressure increases (at $T = \text{constant}$), respectively as temperature decreases (at $p = \text{constant}$) (Fig. 1).

In eqn. (7), the enthalpy of reaction ΔH_T^0 is slightly modified with temperature; therefore, the influence of the temperature on constant K_x (for $p = \text{constant}$) is much higher in case of lower temperatures, which can easily be observed in the particular case of reaction presented in Fig. 1. By similar judgement, we come to the conclusion that the influence of pressure p on the equilibrium constant K_x at $T = \text{constant}$, eqn. (8), is much higher in the domain of low pressures.

Fig. 2. presents the isoconversion curves for the decomposition reaction of magnesium carbonate. The points of the curves were calculated by using eqns. (1) and (3), with necessary data³. In the cross-hatched area, with $\Delta G_T^P < 0$, the chemical equilibrium cannot be attained.

In absence of inert gas, the reaction takes place in monovariant system and the equilibrium is attained only on the curve of normal null affinity ($K_x = 1$), which coincides to the curve of indifferent states⁴. In presence of inert gas, the variance increases by one unit and the equilibrium may be achieved on an infinity of curves, all of them with $0 < K_x < 1$. For example, on the curve with $K_x = 0.1$, the gaseous phase has the unique composition, $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.1$ and $x_{\text{in}} = 0.9$.

Fig. 3 presents the curves $K_x = \text{constant}$ in case of decomposition reaction of ammonium chloride. The points of the curves were calculated by using eqns. (1) and (3), with necessary data³. In the cross-hatched area, the chemical equilibrium cannot be attained. In absence of inert gas, the decomposition takes place in monovariant system, on a single curve with $K_x = 0.25$, on which the gaseous phase has the unique composition $x_{\text{NH}_3} = x_{\text{HCl}} = 0.5$. As monovariant systems are always in a state of indifferent equilibrium, it results that on the curve of indifferent states, the equilibrium constant has the value, $K_x = 0.25$. The other curves with $0 < K_x < 0.25$ can be obtained either in the presence of inert gas, or by not imposing the restrictive condition $x_{\text{NH}_3} = x_{\text{HCl}}$. For any of these curves, there are two equilibrium compositions in absence of inert gas, which are obtained by solving the following system of equations :

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x_{\text{NH}_3} \cdot x_{\text{HCl}} &= K_x \\ x_{\text{NH}_3} + x_{\text{HCl}} &= 1 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

and an infinity of equilibrium compositions in the presence of the inert gas, when the system of eqns. (9) becomes

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x_{\text{NH}_3} \cdot x_{\text{HCl}} &= K_x \\ x_{\text{NH}_3} + x_{\text{HCl}} &= 1 - x_{\text{in}} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10)$$

where x_{in} represent the mole fraction of the inert gas.

Imposing the condition that the discriminant of the quadratic equation resulted from the system (10) should be positive or null, it results that the mole fraction of the inert gas must accomplish the following condition :

$$x_{\text{in}} \leq 1 - 2\sqrt{K_x} \quad (11)$$

Extreme values of the equilibrium constant K_x for equilibrium reaction developing in solid-gas phases, that may take place in a monovariant system : We will take into consideration the same of decomposition of ammonium chloride :

for which the isoconversion curves $K_x = \text{constant}$ are presented in Fig. 3.

The possible values of the equilibrium constant K_x , depending on composition of the gas phase, for both direct and reverse reactions, are indicated in Fig. 4. We can observe that, for the situation in which the decomposition reaction take place in monovariant system (in absence of inert gas), when the gas phase has the unique composition, $x_{\text{NH}_3} = x_{\text{HCl}} = 1/2$, the equilibrium constant K_x has a maximum value, $K_x = 1/4$, in the point M_1 . If we take into account the reverse reaction, also developing in a monovariant system, then the equilibrium constant K'_x has a minimum value, $K'_x = 4$, on the point m_1 . In presence of inert gas, we obtain the curves 2, 3 and 4 (in case of direct reaction) which present maximum values for the K_x on the points M_2 , M_3 and M_4 , respectively, and the curves 2', 3' and 4' (in case of reverse reaction) with minimum values of K'_x on points m_2 , m_3 and m_4 .

In points of maximum or minimum values, $x_{\text{NH}_3} = x_{\text{HCl}} = (1 - x_{\text{in}})/2$, or the molar ratio $\text{NH}_3 : \text{HCl} = 1 : 1$ corresponds to the stoichiometry of the reaction. All the curves are symmetrical to the corresponding verticals that join the points of maximum to those of minimum, and the points of maximum values are situated on a parabola with the equation, $K_x = x_{\text{HCl}}^2$.

We can observe that, in case of direct reaction, as the

Fig. 4. Variation of the equilibrium constant K_x depending on the composition of the gas phase for the reaction: $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}_{(s)} + \text{'In'} \leftrightarrow \text{NH}_3 + \text{HCl} + \text{'In'}$; $K_x = x_{\text{NH}_3} \cdot x_{\text{HCl}}$. In case of reverse reaction, the equilibrium constant is K'_x where $K'_x = 1/K_x$. Curves 1 and 1': $x_{\text{in}} = 0$; curves 2 and 2': $x_{\text{in}} = 0.1$; curves 3 and 3': $x_{\text{in}} = 0.2$; curves 4 and 4': $x_{\text{in}} = 0.3$.

concentration of inert gas increases, the maximum value of the equilibrium constant K_x decreases; we obtain the highest value of the constant K_x in point M_1 , when the reaction takes place in a monovariant system. On the contrary, in case of reverse reaction, the minimum value of constant K'_x increases according to the increase of the concentration of inert gas; we obtain the lowest value of K'_x in point m_1 , when the reaction develops in the same monovariant system.

In order to generalize results presented above, we will take into consideration the following equilibrium solid-gas reaction :

where $\text{P}_1, \text{P}_2, \text{P}_3, \dots$ are products, with equilibrium mole fractions x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots

In absence of inert gas, the reaction takes place in a monovariant system, if mole fractions are directly

proportional to the stoichiometric coefficients :

$$\frac{x_1}{\nu_1} = \frac{x_2}{\nu_2} = \frac{x_3}{\nu_3} = \dots \quad (13)$$

and sum

$$x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots = 1 \quad (14)$$

In presence of inert gas, the reaction takes place in a divariant or multivariant system ($l \geq 2$).

We will demonstrate that in case of equilibrium solid-gas reactions developing in a monovariant or multivariant system (the presence or absence of inert gas presenting no importance), the equilibrium constant K_x has an extreme value, when mole fractions are directly proportional with stoichiometric coefficients; this value is maximum in case of direct reaction (with volume increase) and minimum in case of reverse reaction.

For the general reaction (12), the equilibrium constant K_x has the following expression :

$$K_x = x_1^{\nu_1} \cdot x_2^{\nu_2} \cdot x_3^{\nu_3} \dots \quad (15)$$

where mole fractions x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots have variable values, on the condition that

$$x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots + x_{\text{in}} = 1 \quad (16)$$

By applying the logarithm to eqn. (15),

$$\ln K_x = \nu_1 \ln x_1 + \nu_2 \ln x_2 + \nu_3 \ln x_3 + \dots$$

and then by differentiating the result, on the condition that $K_x = \text{maximum}$, we obtain,

$$\nu_1 \frac{dx_1}{x_1} + \nu_2 \frac{dx_2}{x_2} + \nu_3 \frac{dx_3}{x_3} + \dots = 0 \quad (17)$$

By differentiating eqn. (16), it results,

$$dx_1 + dx_2 + dx_3 + \dots + dx_{\text{in}} = 0 \quad (18)$$

Eqns. (17) and (18) must be simultaneously satisfied.

In order to apply Lagrange's method of undetermined multipliers, we multiply eqn. (18) by the undetermined multiplier λ and the result is added to eqn. (17),

$$\left(\frac{\nu_1}{x_1} + \lambda \right) dx_1 + \left(\frac{\nu_2}{x_2} + \lambda \right) dx_2 + \left(\frac{\nu_3}{x_3} + \lambda \right) dx_3 + \dots + \lambda dx_{\text{in}} = 0 \quad (19)$$

As $dx_i \neq 0, i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ and $\lambda \neq 0$, eqn. (19) is accomplished if the following conditions are satisfied :

$$\frac{\nu_i}{x_i} + \lambda = 0; i = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (20)$$

$$x_{in} = 0 \quad (21)$$

or

$$x_{in} = \text{constant} \quad (22)$$

Eqn. (20) may be written in the form

$$\frac{x_1}{v_1} = \frac{x_2}{v_2} = \frac{x_3}{v_3} = \dots = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots}{v_1 + v_2 + v_3 + \dots} = \frac{1 - x_{in}}{v_1 + v_2 + v_3 + \dots}$$

or

$$x_1 = \frac{v_1(1 - x_{in})}{v_1 + v_2 + v_3 + \dots}; x_2 = \frac{v_2(1 - x_{in})}{v_1 + v_2 + v_3 + \dots};$$

$$x_3 = \frac{v_3(1 - x_{in})}{v_1 + v_2 + v_3 + \dots}; \dots \quad (23)$$

Eqn. (23) shows that in the presence of inert gas (its concentration remaining constant, $x_{in} = \text{constant}$), the equilibrium constant K_x has an extreme value, which is maximum in case of reactions with volume increase and minimum in case of reactions with volume decrease, if mole fractions of the gaseous substances are directly proportional to the stoichiometric coefficients. When the reaction takes place in monovariant system, the concentration of inert gas is zero ($x_{in} = 0$) and the conditions expressed by eqns. (13) and (14) are fulfilled.

If the reaction develops in the same monovariant system, from eqn. (23) it results that the constant K_x of reaction (12) attains the highest value; on the contrary, for the reverse reactions, the constant K'_x attains the lowest possible value. For example, in case of decomposition reaction of NH_4HCO_3 (Fig. 5), the equilibrium constant K_x has a maximum value when the reaction takes place in a monovariant system and $x_{\text{NH}_3} = x_{\text{CO}_2} = x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 1/3$. This value is attained in point 1, placed in the gravity center of equilateral triangle, where $K_x = 1/27 = \text{maximum}$. The closed curves of Fig. 5, symmetrically faced to the bisecting lines, also remain valid in case of reverse reaction, if the equilibrium constant $K'_x = 1/K_x$. In this case, in point 1, the reverse reaction takes place in a monovariant system with $x_{\text{NH}_3} = x_{\text{CO}_2} = x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 1/3$ and $K'_x = 27 = \text{minimum}$.

Influence of inert gas on equilibrium conversion ξ :
The presence of inert gas in the system of reaction has influence on the equilibrium conversion ξ , in case of reactions that take place in isothermal-isobaric conditions, with volume change. For reactions with volume increase ($\Delta n > 0$), the conversion increases in the presence of inert gas; on the contrary, for reactions with volume decrease ($\Delta n < 0$), the value of conversion decreases in the presence of inert gas, and in case of reactions with no volume change ($\Delta n = 0$) the

Fig. 5. Representation of the isoconversion curves $K_x = \text{constant}$ in a triangular diagram for the following reaction :

that takes place in absence of inert gas. The point 1: $K_x = 1/27 = \text{maximum}$; curve 2: $K_x = 1/32$; curve 3: $K_x = 1/40$; curve 4: $K_x = 1/50$.

conversion is not influenced by the presence of inert gas. When reactions take place in isothermal-isochoric conditions, the inert gas does not influence the conversion, independently of the fact that reactions develop with or without volume change.

We will analyze the influence of inert gas on the conversion depending on the conditions of temperature T and pressure p in which the reactions take place. This analysis may easily be performed with the help of isoconversion curves $K_x = \text{constant}$, taking into account the well-known fact that the value of the equilibrium constant K_x depends on the temperature T and pressure p .

We present in Fig. 6 the change of equilibrium conversion $|\Delta\xi|$, taken as module, as a function of $\log K_x$, in case of five chemical reactions (the first three of them with volume decrease, and the last two with volume increase). The quantity $|\Delta\xi|$ was calculated for high increases of concentration of inert gas, from $x_{in,1} = 0$ to $x_{in,2} = 0.8$. In case of reaction with volume increase, $\Delta\xi > 0$; on the contrary, for reactions with volume decrease, $\Delta\xi < 0$. That is why we preferred to represent the module of quantity, $|\Delta\xi|$. As a result, we obtain curves of maximum, phenomenon that appears in case of all chemical reactions which take place with volume change.

An interesting fact is that the maximums of the curves are placed in the neighbourhood of the normal null affinity curve, $K_x = 1$. In other words, the influence of inert gas on

Fig. 6. $|\Delta\xi|$ as a function $\log K_x$ in case of a few chemical reactions, when the mole fraction of the inert gas increases from $x_{in,1} = 0$ to $x_{in,2} = 0.8$, and reactants mix stoichiometrically :

Curve 1 : $N_2 + 3H_2 \leftrightarrow 2NH_3$; $\xi = x_{NH_3}/(x_{NH_3} + 2x_{N_2})$; $\Delta n/n_g = -1/3$.

Curve 2 : $CO + 2H_2 \leftrightarrow CH_3OH_{(g)}$; $\xi = x_{CH_3OH}/(x_{CH_3OH} + x_{CO})$; $\Delta n/n_g = -1/2$.

Curve 3 : $2NO + O_2 \leftrightarrow 2NO_2$; $\xi = x_{NO_2}/(x_{NO_2} + x_{NO})$; $\Delta n/n_g = -1/5$

Curve 4 : $CH_4 + H_2O_{(g)} \leftrightarrow CO + 3H_2$; $\xi = x_{CO}/(x_{CH_4} + x_{CO})$; $\Delta n/n_g = 1/3$.

Curve 5 : $C_{(s)} + CO_2 \leftrightarrow 2CO$; $\xi = x_{CO}/(x_{CO} + 2x_{CO_2})$; $\Delta n/n_g = 1/3$.

conversion is maximum, if the reaction takes place in conditions of temperature T and pressure p situated in the neighbourhood of the normal null affinity curve.

As the values of temperature T and pressure p are placed increasingly far from the curve with $K_x = 1$, the influence is accordingly lesser. We may also obtain curves that are similar to those presented in Fig. 6, for low or medium increases of the inert gas concentration, cases in which the maximums may be slightly displaced; nevertheless, the maximum influence operates in the neighbourhood of normal null affinity curve.

If v_p represents the volume of products, and v_r the volume of reactants, then we may introduce the following quantity for any chemical reaction :

$$\frac{v_p - v_r}{v_p + v_r} = \frac{\Delta n}{n_g} \quad (24)$$

where n_g represents the total amount of gaseous substances (reactants and products) participating in the reaction (the sum of the stoichiometric coefficients of these substances).

In Fig. 6, we present for every reaction, the value of the ratio $\Delta n/n_g$ which has negative value in case of reactions with volume decrease, and positive value for the reactions with volume increase. One should observe the fact that the ratio $\Delta n/n_g$ does not depend on the form in which the chemi-

cal reaction is written (in the sense that by multiplying the reaction by a positive constant, the ratio remains the same). Moreover, if one takes into account the reverse reaction, the sign of the ratio $\Delta n/n_g$ is changed.

The data presented in Fig. 6 show that, for reactions 1, 4 and 5, the maximums of the curves present the value $|\Delta\xi_{\max}| \cong 0,3$, as in case of these reactions $|\Delta n/n_g| = 1/3$. $\Delta\xi_{\max}$ also presents the same value in case of other reactions where the ratio is identical (Table 1). In case of methanol synthesis reaction (Fig. 6), the ratio has a higher value, $\Delta n/n_g = -0,5$, which explains the pronounced maximum of the curve and the pronounced decrease of conversion, $\Delta\xi_{\max} = -0,500$.

Quantitatively, the quantities $|\Delta n/n_g|$ and $|\Delta\xi_{\max}|$ modify in the same sense, which means that the influence of the inert gas increases as the relative change of volume $|\Delta n/n_g|$ corresponding to the reaction, has increasingly higher values. The data presented in Table 1 confirm this matter.

Table 1 presents only reactions with volume decrease. If one takes into account the reverse reactions, then the sign of the quantities $\Delta n/n_g$ and $\Delta\xi_{\max}$ changes, both becoming positive. In order to explain the fact that the sign of $\Delta\xi_{\max}$ changes, we will take into consideration the ammonia synthesis reaction (position 8, Table 1), where the equilibrium conversion ξ is defined. In case of the reverse reaction, $2NH_3 \leftrightarrow N_2 + 3H_2$, the conversion ξ' expresses the fraction of ammonia transformed and is defined by $\xi' = 2x_{N_2}/(2x_{N_2} + x_{NH_3})$. We may observe that the sum of the two conversions equals the unit :

$$\xi + \xi' = 1 \quad (25)$$

a relation that is correct for any chemical reaction. From eqn. (25) we obtain,

$$d\xi + d\xi' = 0; \Delta\xi = -\Delta\xi' \quad (26)$$

In addition, we may also take into account other reactions similar to those presented in the Table 1. For example, reaction (13) is analogous to reactions,

The data presented in the Table 1 show that the change of conversion $|\Delta\xi_{\max}|$ increases continuously according to the relative change of volume $|\Delta n/n_g|$.

Fig. 7 presents $\Delta\xi_{\max}$ depending of $\Delta n/n_g$; the necessary data were taken from Table 1. We also considered the reverse reactions to those presented in Table 1, on the basis of eqn. (26). Thus, we obtain a *unique curve* for all reactions with volume change, from which it results that the change of conversion $\Delta\xi_{\max}$ increases continuously accord-

Table 1. The dependence between the maximum change of equilibrium conversion $\Delta\xi_{\max}$ and the relative change of volume $\Delta n/n_g$, in case of various types of chemical reactions, when the mole fraction of the inert gas increase from $x_{in,1} = 0$ to $x_{in,2} = 0.8$, and the reactants mix stoichiometrically; the equilibrium constant K_x corresponds to quantity $\Delta\xi_{\max}$

Sl. no.	Reaction	Relation of calculation for ξ	$\frac{\Delta n}{n_g}$	$\Delta\xi_{\max}$	K_x
Reaction with decrease of volume ($\Delta n < 0$)					
1.	$8C_{(s)} + 9H_2 \leftrightarrow C_8H_{18(g)}$	$\xi = 9x_{C_8H_{18}} / (9x_{C_8H_{18}} + x_{H_2})$	-0.80	-0.901	550
2.	$6C_{(s)} + 6H_2 \leftrightarrow C_6H_{12(g)}$	$\xi = 6x_{C_6H_{12}} / (6x_{C_6H_{12}} + x_{H_2})$	-0.71	-0.805	20
3.	$C_2H_4 + CO + 2H_2 \leftrightarrow C_3H_7OH_{(g)}$	$\xi = x_{C_3H_7OH} / (x_{C_3H_7OH} + x_{C_2H_4})$	-0.60	-0.643	200
4.	$N_2 + 5/2 O_2 \leftrightarrow N_2O_5$	$\xi = x_{N_2O_5} / (x_{N_2O_5} + x_{N_2})$	-0.56	-0.580	25
5.	$CO + 2H_2 \leftrightarrow CH_3OH_{(g)}$	$\xi = x_{CH_3OH} / (x_{CH_3OH} + x_{CO})$	-0.50	-0.500	10
6.	$6CO + 12H_2 \leftrightarrow C_6H_{12} + 6H_2O_{(g)}$	$\xi = 6x_{C_6H_{12}} / (6x_{C_6H_{12}} + x_{CO})$	-0.44	-0.401	550
7.	$N_2 + 3/2 O_2 \leftrightarrow N_2O_3$	$\xi = x_{N_2O_3} / (x_{N_2O_3} + x_{N_2})$	-0.43	-0.406	10
8.	$N_2 + 3H_2 \leftrightarrow 2NH_3$	$\xi = x_{NH_3} / (x_{NH_3} + 2x_{N_2})$	-0.33	-0.300	10
9.	$CO + 3H_2 \leftrightarrow CH_4 + H_2O_{(g)}$	$\xi = x_{CH_4} / (x_{CH_4} + x_{CO})$	-0.33	-0.298	2.5
10.	$2CO \leftrightarrow C_{(s)} + CO_2$	$\xi = 2x_{CO_2} / (2x_{CO_2} + x_{CO})$	-0.33	-0.300	1
11.	$CO_2 + 4H_2 \leftrightarrow CH_4 + 2H_2O_{(g)}$	$\xi = x_{CH_4} / (x_{CH_4} + x_{CO_2})$	-0.25	-0.215	0.5
12.	$3O_2 \leftrightarrow 2O_3$	$\xi = 3x_{O_3} / (3x_{O_3} + 2x_{O_2})$	-0.20	-0.168	1
13.	$2O_2 + N_2 \leftrightarrow 2NO_2$	$\xi = x_{NO_2} / (x_{NO_2} + 2x_{N_2})$	-0.20	-0.167	5
14.	$CH_2O + H_2O_{(g)} \leftrightarrow CH_3OH_{(g)} + 1/2 O_2$	$\xi = x_{CH_3OH} / (x_{CH_3OH} + x_{CH_2O})$	-0.14	-0.115	1
15.	$HCN + 3H_2O_{(g)} \leftrightarrow CH_4 + NH_3 + 3/2 O_2$	$\xi = x_{NH_3} / (x_{NH_3} + x_{HCN})$	-0.067	-0.056	10
16.	$4NO + 6H_2O_{(g)} \leftrightarrow 4NH_3 + 5O_2$	$\xi = x_{NH_3} / (x_{NH_3} + x_{NO})$	-0.053	-0.043	1
17.	-	Reaction without volume change ($\Delta n = 0$)	0	0	-

Fig. 7. Maximum change of conversion $\Delta\xi_{\max}$ depending on the relative change of volume $\Delta n/n_g$, in case of reactions presented in Table 1.

ing to the relative change of volume $\Delta n/n_g$. We also obtain a single curve in case that the inert gas concentration increases with low and medium values.

References

1. V. Voiculescu and G. Niac, *Rev. Chim. (Bucharest)*, 1978, **29**, 1026; V. Voiculescu, *Rev. Chim. (Bucharest)*, 1985, **36**, 136; V. Voiculescu, L. Simoiu and G. Niac, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1998, **75**, 203.
2. V. Voiculescu, G. Niac and L. Simoiu, *Ann. Univ. Craiova Chim.*, 1995, **2**, 237; V. Voiculescu, G. Niac, M. Mateescu and P. Rotaru, *Ann. Univ. Craiova Chem.*, 1998, **27**, 54; V. Voiculescu, Al. Popescu, M. Mateescu and P. Rotaru, *Ann. Univ. Craiova Chem.*, 1999, **28**, 54, 60.
3. N. M. Baron, E. I. Kviat, E. A. Padgornaia, A. M. Ponomareva and A. A. Raveli, "Kratkii Spravotchnik Fizico-Himiceskih Velicin", Himia, Leningrad, 1972.
4. I. Prigogine and R. Defay, "Chemical Thermodynamics", Longmans, London, 1967.